

SYNTHESES IN THE ACRIDINE SERIES. PART II. 4-METHOXY-
6-CHLORO-9 (DIALKYLAMINOALKYL) AMINOACRIDINES

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Seven N-substituted 4-methoxy-6-chloro-9-aminoacridines have been prepared.

The transfer of chlorine atom from position 6 to 7 in the aterbrin molecule [2-methoxy-6-chloro-9-(*ω*-diethylamino-*isobutyl*) aminoacridine dihydrochloride] has a dystherapeutic effect (Feldmann and Kopeliowitsch, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, 273, 488), but it is not known how any change of the OMe group in the acridine molecule will affect the antimalarial properties. With this idea in view, a number of compounds of the type (I) has been prepared.

[where n is 3, 4 or 5 and R is ethyl, propyl, butyl or amyl].

The position of the chlorine atom has been maintained at 6, using a number of dialkylamino-alkylamino chains at position 9, while the OMe group has been shifted from position 2 to 4.

2 : 4-Dichlorobenzoic acid has been condensed with *o*-anisidine to give 5-chloro-6'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid. This on treatment with phosphoryl chloride gives 4-methoxy-6 : 9-dichloroacridine. Condensation with the appropriate dialkylamino-alkylamine gives the required N-substituted 2-methoxy-6-chloro-9-aminoacridines.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

5-Chloro-6'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—A mixture of 2 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid (19.1g.) (*J. Lahore Phil. Soc.*, 1945, 7, 38), anhydrous potassium carbonate (20 g.), *o*-anisidine (18.5 g.), precipitated copper (0.2 g.) and dry glycerine (50 c.c.) was heated at 160° for 10 hours. The mixture was steam-distilled and the residue was filtered hot (charcoal). After cooling it was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid until acidic to Congo red. A deep violet mass appeared which was filtered and washed with hot water. The product was dissolved in ammonia (charcoal) and then decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid. Another precipitation gave the acid as a cream coloured precipitate. After drying, it was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as buff coloured crystals, m. p. 205-06°, yield 60%. (Found : N, 5.05. C₁₄H₁₂O₃NCl requires N, 5.04 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6 : 9-dichloroacridine.—The above acid (10 g.) was refluxed with freshly distilled phosphoryl chloride (80 c.c.) for 8 hours. Excess of phosphorus oxychloride was removed under vacuum and the residue treated with 10% solution of ice-cold ammonia. A greenish yellow mass was obtained, which after drying in a vacuum desiccator was crystallised from dry benzene as bright yellow needles, m. p. 189-91°, yield 70%. (Found : N, 5.18. $C_{14}H_9ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 5.03 per cent). This acridine is unstable and changes to the corresponding acridone after sometime on exposure. For condensation, it was immediately used after crystallisation.

4-Methoxy-6-chloro-9-(γ -diethylaminopropyl)aminoacridine Dihydrochloride : (General Method).—4-Methoxy-6 : 9-dichloroacridine (2.78 g., 1 mol) was dissolved in freshly distilled phenol (10 g.) and γ -diethylaminopropylamine (1.32 g., 1.1 mol.) was added. The mixture was heated at 100° for 3 hours. After cooling, it was poured into 150 c.c. of ether. Phenol was removed by washing with excess of 2*N*-sodium hydroxide solution. The yellow ethereal extract was filtered to remove any suspended acridone. The acridine base was extracted by shaking with excess of 5% acetic acid. The acetate solution after filtration was decomposed with alkali and the base was again shaken up in ether. After drying the ethereal extract over anhydrous potassium carbonate, the dihydrochloride was precipitated by addition of alcoholic hydrogen chloride. Extreme difficulty was encountered during the crystallisation of the hydrochloride, which usually separated as an oil. In one experiment, it was crystallised from a mixture of absolute methanol and ether as a yellow powder, m. p. 235-36° (decomp.). This observation could not, however, be repeated. The meconate was successfully prepared by treatment of the ethereal extract of the acridine base with a saturated solution of meconic acid in absolute alcohol. A yellow semi-solid was obtained which was thoroughly washed with ether. It was crystallised from absolute ethanol as a yellow powder, m. p. 160° (decomp.). It is quite soluble in water. (Found : N, 7.51. $C_{21}H_{26}ON_3Cl$. $C_7H_4O_7$ requires N, 7.34 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6-chloro-9-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)aminoacridine Dipicrate.—The hydrochloride as well as the meconate could not be crystallised, as they always separated as oils. The dry ethereal extract of the acridine base was concentrated till all ether had evaporated off. The residue was dissolved in dry benzene and treated with a solution of picric acid in benzene. A yellow semi-solid separated at once, which after trituration was converted into a powder. It was thoroughly washed with benzene, till the washings were colourless. The dipicrate was crystallised from absolute ethanol as a yellow microcrystalline powder, m. p. 191-92°. (Found : N, 14.78. $C_{22}H_{28}ON_3Cl$. $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.94 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6-chloro-9-(ϵ -diethylaminoamyl)aminoacridine Dipicrate.—The dihydrochloride as well as the meconate could not be characterised. The picrate was twice crystallised from absolute ethanol as a yellow powder. It shrinks a little at 135° and melts at 151-53°. (Found : N, 15.08. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_3Cl$. $2C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.69 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6-chloro-9-(γ-di-n-propylaminopropyl) aminoacridine Meconate.—The dihydrochloride could not be crystallised. The meconate was crystallised from absolute ethanol as a light yellow powder, m. p. 183-85° (decomp.). It is freely soluble in water. (Found : N, 7.21. $C_{23}H_{30}O N_3Cl$. $C_7H_4O_7$ requires N, 7.0 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6-chloro-9-(γ-di-n-butylaminopropyl) aminoacridine Dipicrate.—The dihydrochloride could not be crystallised. The meconate was prepared in the usual way, but during crystallisation from absolute ethanol, it was converted into white 4-methoxy-6-chloroacridone, m. p. 277-78°. (Found : N, 5.59. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.39 per cent). The picrate was crystallised from a large volume of absolute alcohol as a yellow powder, m. p. 196-98°. (Found : N, 14.01. $C_{25}H_{34}ON_3Cl$. $2 C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 14.23 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6-chloro-9-(γ-di-n-amylaminopropyl) aminoacridine Meconate.—The dihydrochloride could not be characterised. The meconate was crystallised from absolute ethanol as a yellow powder, m.p. 205-06° (decomp.). It is soluble in water. (Found : N, 6.51. $C_{27}H_{38}ON_3Cl$. $C_7H_4O_7$ requires N, 6.40 per cent).

4-Methoxy-6-chloro-9-(γ-piperidinopropyl) aminoacridine dihydrochloride was crystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ether. It forms a stable hydrate which does not show a sharp melting point. It was crystallised thrice from absolute ethanol-ether mixture as a yellow powder. After drying in an air-oven at 100° for 3 hours, it melted at 240° with decomposition. It is freely soluble in water. (Found : N, 9.18. $C_{22}H_{26}ON_3Cl$. $2HCl$ requires N, 9.20 per cent).

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